

DEVELOPMENT OF A PRODUCT PRODUCTION RATE OPTIMIZATION MODEL: A CASE STUDY OF BOPLAS PLASTIC INDUSTRY

¹Abba-Aji, M, ²El_Jumma, A.M and ³Ngala, G.M.
¹Department of Mechanical Engineering University of Maiduguri

ABSTRACT

Linear programming was used to study an optimization problem of BOPLAS, a plastic industry in Maiduguri, North eastern Nigeria. Data obtained from: interaction with the company personnel through verbal interviews, reviewing the company's annual reports and taking reading from the machine in operation were used to generate equations employing the simplex method. The academic version of the software, Costenbol, was used to solve the equations and the value obtained from the objective function was 47.150, with the production rate of 23,187units water jugs per month and 37,738 was hand bowls per month yielding a profit margin of ₦2, 059,808:00 per month. These are 1.01% and 1.60% higher than the current levels of production.

KEYWORDS: Optimization, Linear Programming, Simplex Method, Production, Software, Production.

INTRODUCTION

Considering the rapid changes of technological advancement in Nigeria today, and the replacement of locally manufactured metallic products by plastic products produced by medium scale industry, there is a need to optimize the cost of production of such products. Therefore this study intends to develop a production rate optimization model. The ESA (European space agency) Costing Model, conceived as a tool for making independent price assessment and cost estimation was reviewed. The methods adopted by ESA are estimation by analogy, use of cost estimation relationships and parametric cost modelling. (Fateling, 2000)

The objectives, after obtaining cost data and the industry's periodic reports are: (a) to develop a linear programming model to solve allocation problem of plastic products; and (b) to compare the company's profit with the model to that without the model and suggest remedial measures, if necessary. These objectives can be achieved without the analysis of the initial fixed capital investment, even though it has a direct influence on the final product cost. (Hussey, 1989)

This study has concentrated on the application of plastics in the production of domestic household such as buckets, kettles, water jugs, sacks and polythene bags. The implementation of operating cost control; scheduling and the use of resources were assumed to be appropriate.

Simplex Method Algorithm

High customer demands for water jugs, wash hand bowls, big bowls, packer and hanger were noticed within the period of August and February of every year for the past three years, but the company was uncertain of the optimal allocation of proportions of the products, for instance A-water jugs, B-wash hand bowls, C- big bowls, D-packers, E-hangers. The contribution to profit and overhead per unit of each item is determined. The company was uncertain about how many of each item to produce in order to maximizes its profit; considering x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 and x_5 to be respective proportions of the items to be produced. These are the decision variables of the model, and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ and ϵ are the duration of injection (I), charge (C) and cooling (G) of the five items respectively. An experience machine operator assigns the maximum time to the injection moulding machine through the function setting of a mini computer attached to it. The contributions to profit of the products A, B, C, D and E are a, b, c, d and e respectively.

The simplex equations can then be written as;
Maximize $ax_1 + bx_2 + cx_3 + dx_4 + ex_5$ subject to

$$\text{Injection } \alpha_i x_1 + \beta_i x_2 + \gamma_i x_3 + \delta_i x_4 + \epsilon_i x_5 \leq C_i$$

$$\text{Charge } \alpha_c x_1 + \beta_c x_2 + \gamma_c x_3 + \delta_c x_4 + \epsilon_c x_5 \leq C_{II}$$

$$\text{Cooling } \alpha x_1 + \beta x_2 + \gamma x_3 + \delta x_4 + \epsilon x_5 \leq C_{III}$$

Where $x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5 \geq 0$ (non-negativity constraint) (Krawjewski, 1987)

Injection Moulding Process

Injection moulding is one of the most important plastic moulding processes. It is carried out usually on horizontal hydraulic press. Granular thermoplastic materials are gravity fed from a hopper into a pressure chamber ahead of a plunger. The moving plunger causes the granular plastic to be compressed and then forced through a heating cylinder to palletize it. A torpedo shaped object in the centre of the heating cylinder facilitates uniform heating. The palletized plastic is then injected through an injection nozzle at a high pressure into the die cavity to form the required component. The die is water cooled; making the injected plastic to freeze almost immediately the die cavity is filled. The plunger returns, and the mould opens to eject the form material. The mould closes and the cycle is repeated. In modern machines, as used in the company, the feed plunger is replaced with a motor driven screw plasticizer. It serves both the function of part-heating the plastic granules by internal shear and feeding it to the mould. (Resistance heater bands are still used on the heating cylinder). The screw plasticizer helps to ensure that the thermoplastic fed through the injector nozzle is maintained at a constant and uniform temperature and viscosity. The process requires the use of expensive dies, usually called moulds; thus its use has to be justified by large production runs. The process is easily automated, and cycle times of just a few seconds are common, making injection moulding the most widely used process for producing plastic items. Also a wide range of shapes and plastic materials can be moulded. (Ibhadode, 2001)

METHODOLOGY

Data related to cost of materials were obtained from the company’s report in Feb, 2005 at BOPLAS plastic company, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria, which include the selling price of finished products, initial cost of raw materials, overhead cost, power and most of the fixed and variable costs. Verbal interviews with five of the technical personnel were also conducted. Constraints such as the hours spent for injection, cooling and charge were recorded directly from the machine, on a mini computer attached to it.

Before the application of the simplex method of linear programming, there is a need to calculate the contribution to profits and overheads of each product in questions.

The contribution to profit of each product could be achieved by the application of marginal costing; the application of the principle that only variable costs are charged to the cost unit. The fixed costs for a particular period must be written off against the total contribution for that period to arrive at the profit. (Hussey, 1989)

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Table 1: List of plastic products produced and their selling price at BOPLAS industry Maiduguri

S/N	Products	Quantity	Current price Naira/qnt	Maximum Quantity(dozen)
1	Kettle	Dozen	420:00	56-60
2	Water jug	Dozen	1,000:00	30-32
3	Wash hand bowl	Dozen	550:00	60-70
4	Big bowl	Dozen	235:00	70-80
5	Bowl(medium)	Dozen	190:00	75-90
6	Bowl(small)	Dozen	150:00	90-130
7	Packer	Dozen	300:00	55-60
8	Hanger	Dozen	235:00	70-80
9	25-litre plastic tin	1 unit	220:00	-
10	Polythene bag	10,000pcs	3500:00	18-25
11	Big kettle	Dozen	1,120:00:00	45-50

* 1dozen = 12 units

As earlier mentioned, demands for some products in the list given in Table 1 are high within the period of August to February of the proceeding year, and this occurrence is periodic in nature. Therefore a short term analysis of one month is considered in this work.

Analysis of volume (expected quantity sold per month) and sales:

Individual product sales are determined to obtain the total sales of the company per month. Referring to Table 1, quantity produced per day and product selling price were given, hence the quantity per month and sales can easily be determined. For example, the production of water jug was 31 dozen or 372 unit per day for a six-day work week and 4-weeks per month, the monthly production 8,929 units yielding, at ₦83:33 unit selling price, or ₦744,053:57 per month. Likewise the monthly revenues for wash hand bowls, big bowls, packer and hanger were computed.

Table 2: Divisions and sections of the BOPLAS Industry, Maiduguri

DIVISION	PROCESS UED
Polythene bag section*	Blown film process
Woven sack	Extrusion
Plastic	1. Injection moulding 2. Blown film moulding

* In plastic division

Table 2 shows the Divisions and Sections of the BOPLAS Industry Maiduguri

Table 3 Polypropylene (Pp) woven sack selling price

Pp woven sack (per bale)	₦ per bale	Unit Price (bale per 500)	Price(₦) per month
100kg	19,500:00	39	51,660:00
50kg(large)	15,500:00	31	632,400:00
50kg(small)	14,500:00	25	5,916,000:00

(BOOLAST field survey, 2005)

A bale of 100kg is ₦19, 500:00 and 12bales/day which is equivalent to ₦23, 400:00/day is used yielding revenue of ₦516, 600:00:00/month. Similarly for 50kg/bale (small), 17 bales/day are used for revenue of ₦5, 916, 000:00/month. The total sale for Pp-woven sack is then ₦1, 280, 1600:00.

Polythene bags

The company used 25.5 dozens per day which is 258 units per day yielding revenue of ₦1, 806, 000:00. Total sales for the three divisions/sections of the company were obtained by simple summing the sales in the Pp-injection and blow-film moulding, woven sack and polythene bags division. Revenue of ₦23, 003, 059:97 was realised.

Raw materials cost analysis: the cost of raw materials used in the industry including cost of additives are analysed to arrive at the total cost raw materials used in a month. For Pp-injection moulding division a metric tonne costs ₦203, 500:00 which is equivalent to ₦206:50/kg and 18 bags of 25kg is used. There the cost of Pp-injection per month used was ₦ 2, 230, 200:

High density polyethylene (HPDE)

For pure material 80mm kettle, 9bags per day was used which costs ₦43,875:00 and for 100mm 25-litre can, 14 bags of 25kg per day was used which costs ₦68,250:00 per day. The costs ₦2, 691,000:00 per month for the two items were ₦1, 053,000:00 and ₦1, 638,000:00 respectively.

Deluxtrine: This provides the texture quality of the finished products. 5.25kg which is 25kg/4 will be mixed with 40bags of Pp-raffia, and 18 bags of Pp-raffia are used per day. Therefore the cost of using deluxtrine per month was ₦23, 262:75.

Assorted master batch:

These are responsible for colouring the finished products. The master batch is grouped as;

Table 4 Appropriate colour for master batch used for a given process

PROCESS	COLOUR
1. Injection and blow film moulding	1. T-green, red and orange
2. Extrusion moulding (for Pp-sack)	2. White

(BOPLAST, 2005)

Cost per ton is ₦534, 000 equivalents to ₦534/kg. The costs for T- green and red master batch used per month are ₦2, 221:44 and ₦2, 416:66 respectively. A total cost of raw materials was obtained by summing all the costs in various sections and units of company, yielding ₦7, 146,900:85.

Lubricants/fuels:

1. Rubin S.; this costs ₦5, 400:00 per litre can and the company used 8-can every month, hence ₦43, 200:00 per month was used.

2. Grease; a drum in every five months at a cost of ₦185, 000:00 was used yielding ₦37, 000/month.

Printing Machine Ink; this is of three colours, black, white and green. They are mixed according to customer request and design on the sack produced in the sack section. Half a drum was used in a month at a cost of ₦35,000:00. Summing the two costs of lubricants and printing machine Ink above gives the total cost of ₦1,115,000:00.

From the information gathered from the company, analysis of sales and costs so far carried out, efforts were made to separate variable costs from fixed costs, and then arrived at the profit realized for the month of February 2005. From there, contributions to profit of the products concerned were to generate the equation of the objective function, which is then used to solve the simplex linear equation.

Table 5: Profit statement for the month of February 2005

₦	
Sales;	230, 003, 059:97
LESS VARIABLE COST:	
Materials;	7, 146,900:85
Machine operator's wages;	53, 200:00
Diesel;	1, 250,000:00
Metered power supply;	65, 550:00
Over time;	84, 000:00
Total contribution	<u>9, 078, 450:85</u>
13, 924, 609:12	
LESS FIXED COST;	
Accountants salary	46, 800:00
Courier service	2, 650:00
Communication facilities	16, 500:00
Transportation	84, 000:00
Lubricants/printing Ink	1, 115, 000:00
	<u>686, 150:00</u>
Profit (financial)	13, 238,459:12

The contribution at any given level of sales can be found by using the formula; contribution = sales x p/v ratio

where p = profit, v = volume (Hussey, 1989)

To obtain the contribution per unit product, the unit variable cost must be determined and deducted from the unit sales of the given product. This could be done as;

WATER JUG;	
Variable cost;	₦
Diesel;	$1, 250, 000 / (24 \times 8929) = 5.83/\text{unit}$
Machine operator's wages	$532, 000 / (24 \times 8929) = 2.48/\text{unit}$
Metered power supply;	$65, 550 / (24 \times 8929) = 0.30/\text{unit}$
Materials	$7, 146, 900.85 / (24 \times 8929) = 33.35/\text{unit}$
Over time	$84, 000 / (24 \times 8929) = 0.39/\text{unit}$
Total variable cost	= 42:35
₦	
Selling price per unit	83:33
Variable cost per unit	<u>42:35</u>
Contribution per unit	40:98

Similar procedure can be used to obtain the contribution for the other products of interest. It was then observed that the company was not gaining any contribution to profit by producing 90 to 120 dozens of small bowl at a selling price of ₦12.5/ unit, instead it was losing by 0.01/unit, as a result of this, it was not included in the simplex method analysis. The products to be considered therefore are; water jug, wash hand bowl, big bowl, packer and hanger.

Table5: Product and recorded machine time during process

Process time (sec)	Water jug	Wash bowl	Big bowl	packer	hanger	Constraint (C)
Injection	9.5	7.5	8.0	6.0	8.0	15
Charge	11.3	9.0	10.0	6.0	8.0	14
Cooling	15.0	5.0	6.5	6.0	8.0	15

The proportion to be produced so as to maximize the contribution to profit of each product and the cost implication of adjusting constraints could be achieved by solving the linear programming model. From the analysis above, the equation can be written as;

Maximize $40.98x_1 + 25.62x_2 + 2.65x_3 + 2.61x_4 + 4.23x_5$ subject to

Injection $9.5x_1 + 7.5x_2 + 8x_3 + 6x_4 + 8x_5 \leq 15$

Charge $11.3x_1 + 9x_2 + 10x_3 + 6x_4 + 8x_5 \leq 14$

Cooling $15x_1 + 5x_2 + 6.5x_3 + 6x_4 + 8x_5 \leq 15$

Where $x_1x_2x_3x_4x_5 \geq 0$ (non-negativity constraint) (Krawjewski, 1987)

A computer programme, academic version software was used to solve the generated equations and obtain the following results;

Value of the objective function = 47.150, yield $x_1 = 8280$, $x_2 = 0.5159$, $x_3 = 0.0$, $x_4 = 0.0$, $x_5 = 0.0$ (Costenoble, 2003)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the results obtained after solving the equations of linear programming, it is obvious that the company (Borno plastic company) should lay more emphasis on the production of water jug and wash hand bowls, when using injection moulding machine.

Since the maximum time the company used was eight hours per day, and the cycle time for water jug and wash hand bowl are 36 and 35.5seconds, the optimum number of the two products to be produced will be:

Water jug; $60 \times 60 \times 8 / 36 \times 0.8280 = 966.15/\text{day}$, yielding a quantity of 23, 187.6/month.

Selling price per month = $23, 187.6 \times 83.33$ (unit price) = ₦1, 932, 222:70

Similar procedure was used to obtain the quantity of 37, 738.968/month yielding a selling price of ₦1, 729, 576:903. These values obtained are now substituted back in the profit statement for the month of February 2005. The difference of these sales values and the initial sales value for the two products are now added to the total sales in the analysis for profit. That is;

₦1, 932, 222:708 (new sales value) – ₦744, 053:57 (initial sales value) = ₦1, 188, 169:138

₦1, 729, 576:903 – ₦857, 937:6 = ₦871, 639:30, adding the two sales we obtained ₦2, 059, 808:39

And the initial total sales value obtained was ₦23, 003, 059:97. Therefore the new total sales value will now be; ₦23, 003, 059:97 + ₦2, 059, 808:39 = ₦25, 062, 868:41

The new profit statement will now be;

₦	
Sales;	25, 062, 868:41
Less total variable cost	<u>9, 078, 450:85</u>
Total contribution	15, 984, 417:56
Less fixed cost	<u>686, 150:00</u>
Profit	15, 298, 267:56

The profit margin can then be obtained when the initial profit is subtracted from the profit obtained above. That is; ₦15, 298, 267:56 – ₦13, 238, 459:12 = ₦2, 059, 808:44

The above analysis shows that, when the optimum number of water jugs and washes hand bowls are produced by the company, the profit obtained by the company within a month will be maximized to ₦2, 059, 808:44

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The optimum number of water jugs and wash hand bowls to be produced by the company will now be 966 and 1,573 units respectively yielding a profit of ₦15, 298,276:56 per month compared with ₦13, 238,459:12 which the company is currently producing for a profit margin of ₦2, 059,808:44. This is a clear justification why the company needs to emphasize the production of water jugs and wash hand bowls with regards to injection moulding machine. The company should also concentrate on other products (big bowls, packer and hanger) discuss in this analysis in other to improve their selling prices, taking into cognizance the quality of the products and customer requirements.

This work is recommended as a good starting point to help managers in decision making. The manager can carryout sensitivity analysis by adjusting some constraints in the linear equations, then simulate and compare the results to know which constraint is critical.

Apart from the time constraint considered in this work, temperature is another constraint that affects the production of plastics. Further research can then be carried out when temperature constraints from various divisions/sections of the industry were obtained. The procurement of raw materials is a major problem facing plastic industries in Nigeria. The should encourage petrochemical industries producing plastic raw materials, like the one in Port Harcourt, to be in full production. That will reduce the cost of importing raw materials from abroad. Also foreign raw materials have a very low melting point compared to the one produced in Nigeria. This is not pleasant for moulding process. Finally, it is strongly recommended that Nigerian industries should adopt the modern operation research techniques to obtain optimum results and proper decisions.

REFERENCES

- Costenoble R. (2003). “Simplex Method of Solving General Linear Programming problems”
- Fateling K. (2003). “ESA Cost Modeling, European Space Agency” USA America McGraw Hill Publishing Company.
- Hussey R. (1989). “Cost and Management Accounting P (118-125)” Macmillan Professional Master
- Ibhadode A. O. (2001) “Introduction to Manufacturing Technology” P (92-95), AMBIK Publishers, Lagos
- Krawjewski J. Larry P. Ritz man (1987). “Operations Management; Strategy and Analysis” P (appx. C3-C22) Addison-Wesley Publishing Company Published by Addison-Wesley Publishing Company
www.estec.esa.nl/eawww
www.Zweigmedia.com/third Edsite/index.htm

Received for Publication: 13/05/09

Accepted for Publication: 10/07/09

Corresponding Author

Abba-Aji

Department of Mechanical Engineering University of Maiduguri

E-mail: birma4real2004@yahoo.com